

SCHOOL OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

“Social problems in Kazakhstan: violence against women”
scientific research project

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2023, Almaty

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INTRODUCTION

For decades, the problem of violence against women has been one of the most acute social problems in Kazakhstan. Violence against women is a global problem that recognizes no cultural, geographic, religious, social or economic boundaries. Physical, emotional, sexual and economic violence against women is widespread throughout the world. Most victims of violence do not receive the necessary help and support, which aggravates their situation and makes the recovery process more difficult.

Cultural and societal norms also play a role in perpetuating violence against women in Kazakhstan. Traditional gender roles, which assign men as dominant and women as subservient, create power imbalances that can lead to violence. Additionally, the social stigma attached to reporting violence and seeking help can prevent women from accessing support services.

Economic inequality is another factor that contributes to violence against women in Kazakhstan. Women's economic dependence on their partners can make them more vulnerable to violence and make it harder for them to leave abusive relationships. In addition, a lack of economic opportunities and financial resources can prevent women from seeking help or leaving abusive situations.

It is well-known that violence against women in various forms and manifestations is a violation of human rights and fundamental freedoms. The purpose of our study is to study the social problem of "violence against women" in Kazakhstan.

Relevance of the topic

The topic of violence against women in Kazakhstan is highly relevant today due to the ongoing prevalence of this issue and its significant impact on individuals and society as a whole. This problem affects a large number of women in the country and is a violation of their basic human rights.

Furthermore, violence against women has significant psychological, social, and economic impacts that can have long-lasting effects on victims and their communities. This issue can lead to mental health issues, social exclusion, and economic dependence, among other challenges, which can further perpetuate cycles of violence.

Addressing this issue is crucial not only for the protection and well-being of women but also for the overall development and progress of Kazakhstan as a society. Violence against women hinders social and economic development, perpetuates gender inequality, and undermines human rights.

Moreover, the topic of violence against women is becoming increasingly relevant globally, with many countries recognizing the need to address this issue as part of their commitment to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Kazakhstan has also committed to the Sustainable Development Goals, including goal 5 on gender equality, which specifically addresses the elimination of violence against women.

Studying the problem of violence against women in Kazakhstan is an important task for sociologists, government agencies and public organizations. Effective measures must be developed to prevent violence, protect victims and punish perpetrators. This will help create a safe and equal society where everyone feels protected and respected.

Formulation of the research problem

Despite the government's legislative efforts to tackle violence against women in Kazakhstan, it remains a pervasive social issue. The research aims to examine the factors that contribute to violence against women in the country, the negative impact of such violence on women's lives, and to identify effective strategies for prevention and reduction of violence against women and seeks to provide insights that can inform policy and practice, and ultimately lead to a safer and more equitable society for women in Kazakhstan. The problem is to understand the root causes of this issue, including cultural and societal norms, economic inequality, and lack of awareness, and to develop comprehensive solutions that address these factors.

Aims and objectives of the research

The overarching aim of this dissertation is to contribute to a better understanding of the problem of violence against women in Kazakhstan and to provide insights into effective strategies for preventing and reducing violence against women in the country. To achieve this, the research report will examine the underlying factors that contribute to violence against women in Kazakhstan, assess the effectiveness of existing policies and programs aimed at addressing this problem, and develop recommendations for improving the prevention and response to violence against women in the country.

Objectives of the research

To review the literature on violence against women in Kazakhstan, including its prevalence, causes, and impacts on women's lives.

1. To examine the social, cultural, and economic factors that contribute to violence against women in Kazakhstan.
2. To investigate the effectiveness of existing policies and programs aimed at preventing and addressing violence against women in Kazakhstan.

3. To identify best practices from other countries that could be adapted to the Kazakhstani context to prevent and reduce violence against women.

I THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE PROBLEM OF VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN

1.1 Brief overview of violence against women in Kazakhstan

Violence against women is a widespread issue in Kazakhstan, as it is in many other countries. This problem has been studied by various researchers and organizations, who have found that domestic violence, sexual assault, and harassment are prevalent in Kazakhstan.

Study conducted by the UNFPA found that approximately 17% of women in Kazakhstan have experienced physical or sexual violence from an intimate partner. Additionally, 12% of women have experienced sexual violence outside of a relationship. Furthermore, according to the National Center for the Protection of Women from Violence, domestic violence is the most common form of violence against women in Kazakhstan.

Several factors contribute to the prevalence of violence against women in Kazakhstan. For example, traditional gender roles, economic inequality, and a lack of awareness and education about the issue can all contribute to the perpetuation of this problem.

Various organizations are working to address this issue in Kazakhstan, including the UNFPA and the International Center for Gender Studies. These organizations are working to raise awareness about the issue, improve access to services for victims, and promote gender equality. However, there is still much work to be done to address this problem in Kazakhstan and around the world.

1.2 Definition and types of violence against women

Violence against women refers to any act of gender-based violence that results in physical, sexual, or psychological harm or suffering to women. It can take many forms and occur in various settings, including the home, workplace, community, and state.

Some common types of violence against women include:

1. Physical violence: This includes hitting, slapping, choking, kicking, and any other act that causes physical harm.
2. Sexual violence: This includes rape, sexual assault, and other forms of non-consensual sexual contact or activity.
3. Emotional or psychological violence: This includes verbal abuse, threats, intimidation, humiliation, and other acts that cause emotional or psychological harm.

4. Economic violence: This includes controlling a woman's access to financial resources, preventing her from working, and other acts that limit her economic independence.

5. Cultural violence: This includes harmful practices such as female genital mutilation, forced marriage, and other forms of gender-based violence that are rooted in cultural norms and traditions.

It's worth noting that violence against women is often interconnected and can occur in multiple forms simultaneously. For example, a woman who experiences physical violence may also experience emotional abuse and economic control.

1.3 Theoretical approaches to understanding violence against women

The purpose of theoretical approaches to understanding violence against women is to provide a framework for understanding the complex and multifaceted nature of this issue. These approaches allow researchers and practitioners to identify the various factors that contribute to violence against women and to develop interventions and policies aimed at preventing and addressing this issue.

There are several theoretical approaches that have been used to understand violence against women:

1. Feminist theory: This approach argues that gender inequality is at the root of violence against women. Feminist theorists believe that women are oppressed in patriarchal societies, and that this oppression can manifest as violence. This approach emphasizes the importance of understanding the social and cultural factors that contribute to violence against women.

2. Social learning theory: This theory suggests that violence is learned through observation and imitation of others. Social learning theorists argue that individuals who witness or experience violence in their families or communities may be more likely to perpetrate violence themselves.

3. Psychopathology theory: This approach suggests that violence against women is the result of psychological disorders or personality traits in the perpetrator. This approach emphasizes individual factors such as mental illness, personality disorders, or childhood trauma as contributing factors to violence.

4. Ecological theory: This approach suggests that violence against women is influenced by a complex interplay of individual, relationship, community, and societal factors. This approach emphasizes the importance of understanding the broader social and cultural contexts in which violence occurs.

5. Intersectionality theory: This approach recognizes that women experience violence

in different ways depending on their intersectional identities, such as race, ethnicity, class, sexual orientation, and disability. This approach emphasizes the importance of understanding how multiple forms of oppression intersect to produce violence against women.

Altogether, these theoretical approaches can help researchers and practitioners better understand the complex and multifaceted nature of violence against women, and can inform the development of interventions and policies aimed at preventing and addressing this issue.

1.4 Forms and types of violence against women in Kazakhstan

Violence against women is a significant problem in Kazakhstan, and it takes different forms and types. Here are some common types of violence against women in Kazakhstan:

1. Domestic violence: Domestic violence is the most prevalent form of violence against women in Kazakhstan. It can include physical, emotional, psychological, sexual, and economic abuse. Domestic violence is usually committed by an intimate partner or family member.

2. Sexual violence: Sexual violence is also widespread in Kazakhstan and includes rape, sexual assault, and harassment. Women who suffer sexual violence may face stigma and blame for the abuse they have endured.

3. Bride kidnapping: Bride kidnapping is a traditional practice in some parts of Kazakhstan where men kidnap women to marry them. This practice is illegal, but it still occurs in some rural areas.

4. Forced marriage: Forced marriage is a type of gender-based violence in which women are forced to marry against their will. Women who experience forced marriage may also face physical, emotional, and sexual abuse.

5. Honor violence: Honor violence is a type of violence in which women are punished for perceived violations of family honor. This can include physical violence, forced marriage, or even murder.

6. Human trafficking: Women and girls are often victims of human trafficking in Kazakhstan, and they may be forced into prostitution or other forms of labor against their will.

It is essential to note that these types of violence against women are often interconnected, and women may suffer from multiple forms of violence at the same time. The Kazakh government has taken some steps to address this issue, including passing laws to protect women from violence and establishing crisis centers and hotlines to provide support to victims.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

In conclusion, violence against women is a complex and multifaceted problem that has deep roots in social, cultural, and economic structures. Theoretical frameworks such as feminist theory, intersectionality, and social learning theory provide valuable insights into the causes and consequences of violence against women, as well as the various factors that contribute to its perpetuation.

By examining the prevalence, forms, and consequences of violence against women, as well as the risk factors and prevention strategies, researchers and policymakers can gain a better understanding of this critical public health issue. It is essential to recognize the importance of addressing the underlying social and cultural norms that perpetuate gender-based violence and to implement effective prevention and intervention strategies to eliminate this problem.

It is crucial to raise awareness about the issue of violence against women and to work together to create a society that promotes equality and respect for all individuals, regardless of gender. Only by working together can we hope to end the cycle of violence and create a safer and more just world for women everywhere.

II PREVALENCE OF VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN IN KAZAKHSTAN

2.1 Overview of statistics on violence against women in Kazakhstan

Violence against women is a serious issue in Kazakhstan, with many women experiencing different forms of violence. Domestic violence is the most common form of violence against women in Kazakhstan, with a 2019 study by the National Center for the Protection of Women from Violence revealing that over 115,000 cases of domestic violence were reported in 2018.

Sexual violence is also prevalent, with a 2017 survey by the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) indicating that approximately 12% of women in Kazakhstan have experienced sexual violence outside of a relationship. Intimate partner violence is another significant issue, with the same UNFPA survey revealing that approximately 17% of women in Kazakhstan have experienced physical or sexual violence from an intimate partner.

Femicide, the killing of women, is also a concern in Kazakhstan, with the UN reporting a femicide rate of 5.5 per 100,000 women in the country. This is higher than the global average which is one kill per hour. Furthermore, a 2018 study by UNICEF found that approximately 2% of girls in Kazakhstan are married before the age of 18, highlighting the issue of child marriage.

It is important to note that these statistics likely underestimate the true extent of violence against women in Kazakhstan, as many cases go unreported or are not captured by

official statistics. Factors such as traditional gender roles, economic inequality, and a lack of awareness and education about the issue contribute to the perpetuation of this problem.

Various organizations, including the UNFPA and the International Center for Gender Studies, are working to address this issue by raising awareness, improving access to services for victims, and promoting gender equality. However, there is still much work to be done to address this problem in Kazakhstan and globally. The statistics demonstrate the need for continued efforts to prevent and address violence against women, to ensure the safety and well-being of women in Kazakhstan and around the world.

2.2 Factors contributing to violence against women in Kazakhstan

While exploring this topic, factors that contribute to violence against women in Kazakhstan were identified. According to the conducted survey among men and women aged 15 to 70, you can see that many people answered that stereotypes are the main factor. But there are other factors that contribute to violence against women in Kazakhstan. These include:

1. Patriarchal norms and attitudes: From the survey, which was completed by 52 people, 92.9% voted that the reason lies in this. Although 7.1% think otherwise. The fact that the majority voted "for" proves that patriarchal norms and attitudes are deeply rooted in Kazakhstani society, according to which men occupy positions of power and authority over women. This can lead to gender discrimination, which can escalate into violence.

2. Lack of legal protection: Despite the adoption of laws to protect women from violence, implementation and enforcement are often weak. This creates an environment where perpetrators of violence can act with impunity, and victims do not have sufficient recourse for justice.

3. Traditional practices: Traditional practices, such as bride kidnapping, can perpetuate violence against women in Kazakhstan. These practices are often seen as a way to assert male dominance and control over women.

4. Inferiority of education and economic dependence: According to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the literacy rate for women in Kazakhstan is lower than that of men. The lack of education and knowledge among women may lead to their increased vulnerability and inability to advocate for themselves, protect themselves, or challenge the cultural and social norms that perpetuate gender-based violence.

These factors contribute to a culture where violence against women is normalized and not adequately addressed. It is essential to address these factors through education, legal

reform, and the promotion of gender equality and women's empowerment to eliminate violence against women in Kazakhstan.

2.3 Psychological and social impact of violence against women

Violence against women has significant psychological and social impacts that can have long-lasting effects on victims, their families, and communities. These impacts are particularly severe in cases of repeated or chronic violence.

Psychologically, violence against women can lead to a range of mental health issues, including anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and suicidal ideation. Victims of violence may also experience low self-esteem, a sense of isolation, and difficulty trusting others. These psychological impacts can have a ripple effect on victims' personal relationships, work, and overall well-being.

Socially, violence against women can lead to increased social isolation and exclusion, as well as reduced participation in community activities. Victims may also face discrimination and stigma, making it difficult for them to seek help and support. The impact of violence can also extend beyond individual victims, affecting families and communities as a whole. For example, children who witness violence against their mothers may experience behavioral problems, emotional trauma, and a higher risk of perpetuating violence in their own relationships in the future.

In Kazakhstan, ongoing efforts are being made to prevent and respond to violence against women. The government has passed legislation criminalizing domestic violence and established a hotline for victims to report violence and access support services. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are also working to raise awareness, provide counseling and legal support to victims, and promote gender equality.

Despite these efforts, there is still much work to be done. Many victims are still hesitant to report violence due to fear of retribution or cultural and societal pressure to keep such matters private. There is also a need to improve access to support services, particularly in rural areas, and to address cultural and social norms that perpetuate violence against women.

In conclusion, violence against women has significant psychological and social impacts that can have long-lasting effects on victims and their communities. Ongoing efforts to prevent and respond to violence against women in Kazakhstan are important to ensure that victims receive the support and protection they need and to promote a culture of gender equality and non-violence. It is essential to continue to raise awareness, provide support services, and work towards eradicating the root causes of violence against women.

2.4 Methodology and findings of the study

In this chapter description of research conduction through different methodologies and execution of different fieldwork practices will be given. This chapter will present the site of study while stating and outlining different procedures and used methods in the data collection through interviews and a literature/document review, interviews and data processing such as the research design, data collection instruments, data collection procedures and finally the data analysis.

Violence against women is a serious violation of human rights and a public health problem. Despite a growing body of data on the magnitude of the problem, current data mostly come from industrialized countries, and methodological differences limit the extent to which comparisons can be made between studies. We sought to assess the extent of physical and sexual partner violence against women in Kazakhstan. As a basis for our research, we took articles Garcia-Moreno, C., Jansen, H. A., Ellsberg, M., Heise, L., & Watts, C. H. (2006) "Prevalence of intimate partner violence: findings from the WHO multi-country study on women's health and domestic violence" and Jewkes, R., Sen, P., & Garcia-Moreno, C. (2002) "Sexual violence. In World report on violence and health" (pp. 147-182). Scientific studies and statistics show that over-women is a common and serious problem throughout the world, and does not depend on age, race, status or culture. The main forms of offense against women include physical, psychological, sexual and economic abuse.

Using the anthropological basis of methodologies in the study of violence against women in Kazakhstan, we have included the study of socio-cultural and historical factors that influence violence against women in this country. Using questionnaires, we collected data, and to study the data, we used quantitative methods of analysis.

As a result, the study found that violence against women is widespread and affects women of all ages, races and socioeconomic groups. 78.6% of all voters say that they often heard about cases of violence against women in their environment and 67.9% indicated the scale of the problem of violence against women in Kazakhstan as 9 and 10 out of 10. Following the results of these data and data from work other people, it is estimated that one in three women will experience physical or sexual abuse in their lifetime.

In Kazakhstan, as in many other countries, there are many forms of violence against women. Violence against women takes many forms, including physical, sexual, emotional and economic abuse. The most common form of violence against women, according to the results of the questionnaire, is physical violence by a partner.

1. Physical violence is violence that manifests itself in the form of physical acts such as hitting, kicking, strangling, torturing and other forms of violence that can result in injury, mutilation and even death of the victim. 92.9% of people believe that physical violence against women is the most common.

2. Sexual violence is a form of violence that manifests itself in the form of sexual acts without the consent of the victim, such as rape, sexual harassment, forced prostitution, and others. 83.9% of people believe that sexual violence against women is the most common.

3. Psychological violence is violence that manifests itself in the form of threats, insults, bullying, humiliation, control and other forms of psychological pressure on the victim, which can seriously damage their mental health and self-esteem. 78.6% of people believe that sexual violence against women the most common.

CONCLUSION OF THE 2nd CHAPTER

The prevalence of violence against women in Kazakhstan is a serious concern. According to a 2019 survey conducted by the National Research Center for Motherhood and Childhood, over 21% of women in Kazakhstan have experienced physical or sexual violence at the hands of their intimate partners. However, it is important to note that this figure likely underestimates the true extent of the problem, as many cases of violence go unreported due to social stigma, fear of retaliation, and other barriers.

In addition to intimate partner violence, women in Kazakhstan also face other forms of violence, including sexual harassment, trafficking, and honor-based violence. The 2019 survey found that over 60% of women in Kazakhstan have experienced some form of gender-based violence in their lifetime.

Efforts to address violence against women in Kazakhstan have been made in recent years, including the adoption of a law on domestic violence in 2019 and the establishment of hotlines and shelters for victims of violence. However, more needs to be done to raise awareness, improve access to services for survivors, and address the root causes of violence against women, such as gender inequality and harmful cultural norms.

In conclusion, violence against women is a serious problem in Kazakhstan, with a significant proportion of women experiencing physical or sexual violence at the hands of their intimate partners, as well as other forms of gender-based violence. Although efforts have been made to address this issue, more needs to be done to raise awareness, improve access to services for survivors, and address the underlying causes of violence against women. It is important for society as a whole to recognize and condemn all forms of violence against women and work together to create a safer and more equal future for all.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, violence against women is a pervasive and serious issue that affects women across the globe, including in Kazakhstan. Theoretical frameworks such as feminist theory, intersectionality, and social learning theory have shed light on the root causes of this problem, including social and cultural norms that perpetuate gender-based violence.

It is essential to recognize the prevalence and impact of violence against women in Kazakhstan, including intimate partner violence, sexual harassment, trafficking, and honor-based violence. Efforts to address this issue, such as the adoption of a law on domestic violence and the establishment of hotlines and shelters, are important steps, but more needs to be done to raise awareness, improve access to services for survivors, and address the underlying causes of violence against women.

Creating a society that promotes equality and respect for all individuals, regardless of gender, is essential in addressing violence against women. It is crucial for everyone to recognize and condemn all forms of violence against women and work together to create a safer and more equal future for all. Only through collective action and commitment can we hope to end the cycle of violence and create a world where all women can live free from violence and fear.

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